

The Theoretical Aspect of Effective Teaching Methods

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Abstract. *This article discusses the theoretical aspects of teaching methods, in particular, the communicative orientation in teaching a foreign language. The methodological principles of communicative methodology are mentioned: interrelated aspects of the study of foreign language culture, including the complex nature of foreign language culture in the manifestation of unity and interrelation of its educational, cognitive, educational and developmental aspects.*

Keywords: *theoretical aspects, methodological principles, communicative methodology, independent thinking.*

Introduction: When studying the basics of teaching a foreign language in this theoretical part of the work, attention should be paid to those basic provisions that reflect and summarize the most essential parts of the activity. This means that the methodological principles underlying teaching are understood as initial statements that define the goals, content, methods and organization of learning and manifest themselves in interconnection and interdependence. In our case, the principles are used to determine the strategy and tactics of teaching English at all stages at almost every point of the educational process. Since as a result of learning a foreign language, the skills of using language as a means of communication are formed, the leading Principle is the principle of communicative orientation. The main function is to create all the conditions for communication: motives, goals and communication problems.

The communicative orientation determines the choice and organization of language material, its situational conditionality, the communicative value of both speech and educational exercises, the communicative formulation of educational tasks, the organization and structure of the lesson. This principle presupposes the creation of conditions for the speech and intellectual activity of students at every moment of learning. English language learning is an integration process, which shows, first of all, that the assimilation of various aspects of the language, its phonetics, grammar, vocabulary does not occur separately as separate discrete components of the language, but is also integrated. Students capture and assimilate them during speech actions, the implementation of which may require the use of words, word forms, phrases, super-phrasal unity and, finally, text, due to communication situations. The teacher performs organizational, educational and supervisory functions. The functions of the student include familiarization with the educational material, training necessary for the formation of language and conversational skills, and There are three main functions that the student performs, and the teacher must organize the student's teaching and direct it.

Main part: Then, the main methods should include familiarity, training and application. Control, including correction and evaluation, is concomitant, as in each of the main methods. I.L. Bim notes that the display is aimed at the sensory perception of students - auditory, visual, motor. The teacher may accompany the presentation with an explanation; An explanation that encourages the student to think is necessary and sufficient for understanding and awareness of the perceived material for the purpose of subsequent meaningful learning and application. The teacher can use different ways of presentation. When applying a new vocabulary, the organizing function of the teacher is most clearly

manifested. He must create favorable conditions, a friendly atmosphere for the normal course of the speech act. He must create such conditions in which each student would like to participate in the work of a group in which children sought to understand the content and meaning of the text they read or listened to, and were not afraid to make mistakes. When applying new vocabulary, the formulation of speech skills is controlled, and it is established how the student can use each of them for practical purposes.

The considered methods reflect the essence of the pedagogical process in which the teacher and students interact. These methods are used in teaching a foreign language at school, reveal the specifics of the subject and are aimed at achieving practical, educational and developmental goals.

The methodological foundations of modern teaching methods for the development of foreign language teaching methods, alternating crises of shortage and overproduction of ideas were necessary for the formation of a new methodological direction. For example, the transition to communicative learning is carried out in the apparent absence of meaningful and really new ideas. The crisis brought to life active methodological and methodological searches that contributed to the development of modern pedagogical concepts of language teaching. To understand what constitutes the basis of modern methods of teaching English, it is necessary to consider in detail the methodological principles that underlie these techniques. The structure of the communicative method includes cognitive, developmental and educational aspects that are aimed at educating the student. Considering this and the concept of communication, as well as the complexity of learning systems, we can formulate the following methodological principles of communicative methodology: interrelated aspects of the study of foreign language culture. The complex nature of foreign language culture is manifested in the unity and interrelation of its educational, cognitive, educational and developmental aspects. In a practical sense, all these aspects are equal. But true mastery of one is possible only with adequate mastery by others. In this regard, any type of work, any exercise in the learning process combines all four aspects of a foreign language culture and is evaluated depending on the availability of these data points.

Real knowledge about culture, linguistics and linguistics cannot be completely reworked in a school course, so you must build a model of a meaningful object of knowledge, which is selected in accordance with the learning objectives and the volume of course content that will be sufficient to represent the culture of the country and the language system. It is also necessary to take into account the cognitive needs of individual students related to their individual interests, etc. The specific amount of training and its ultimate goals require a methodology to create a content development model, that is, a certain minimum that is required to solve problems facing the subject. Any cycle of stages based on the development of skills and abilities in each type of speech activity. A combination of communication and other actions can lead learning to real communication, which takes place not only for communication, but also serves other actions that occur simultaneously. A more productive mastery of all aspects of a foreign language by students provides for a system of tools (memos and special exercises) for the formation of students' skills and abilities to form the ability to learn, which is a subjective individualization. It is important to note that the more independence a student takes, the more effectively he learns. Therefore, in this method, great attention is paid to the development of independent thinking, in particular, when discussing problems. The principle of novelty in teaching foreign languages. The training is structured in such a way that all its content and organization are permeated with novelty. prescribes the use of texts and exercises that contain something new for students, the refusal to repeatedly read the same text and exercises with the same task, a variety of texts of different content, but based on the same material. Thus, the novelty provides involuntary learning, develops students' speech and productive speech abilities, and is of interest for educational activities.

It is important to note that all of the above principles are interrelated, interdependent and mutually reinforcing. Therefore, compliance with the attached system requires compliance with all of the above principles and how they are combined. Now let's turn to the methodological principles that underlie other modern methods of teaching English. A separate cycle is considered as a complete

period of self-study aimed at solving specific tasks in achieving the overall goal of learning English. The principle of autonomy also plays a very important role in the design methodology. To prove this, it is necessary to consider the essence of the conceptual project. A project is a work independently planned and implemented by trainees, in which verbal communication is woven into the intellectual and emotional context of other activities (games, travel, etc.). The novelty of this approach lies in the fact that students are given the opportunity to communicate through design content, starting from the first grade. Each project is related to a specific topic and develops within a certain time frame. The work on the project is combined with the creation of a solid language base. And since the work on the project is carried out either by itself or in a group with others, we can talk about the principle of autonomy as one of the fundamental ones. The principles of design methods are closely interrelated and very important. This method teaches students to think creatively and independently, planning their actions can be a solution to the tasks they face, but the principles underlying this method make learning possible for any age group. In conversation, everyone is exposed and exposed.

Conclusion: Especially an important place here is occupied by the knowledge of other people, which is a prerequisite for human communication. It is the core of collective activity and personality in the team. All this leads to a high intensity and density of communication, a variety of forms of work. This encourages teachers to work in a constant search for new forms of presentation. Language skills are formed in non-verbal conditions, fragile. Therefore, the most productive working approach is considered to be the approach to learning a foreign language, involving simultaneous and parallel mastery of language material and speech activity. In the intensive learning system, the met moves use a given grammatical form in a series of exercises in which a changing situation is realized with the same communicative intention. The application of an activity-based methodology will make it possible to systematize and synthesize the language and speech experience available to students. The need for this is inherent in the name itself. This method provides great activity in the preliminary development of language tools and subsequent mastery of communication based on existing knowledge, training, skills and the use of language in speech. The principle of the basic means of language proficiency. The techniques described above can be combined under one heading: The best communication training is communication.

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